

Topic : Future of Deep Learning : Capsule Networks and Differential Manifolds

Overview: Deep Learning has shown powerful role in all aspects of modern society, ranging from web search filtering of social network to recommendation engines for e-commerce size to improvements and even sometimes breakthroughs into healthcare in medicine. However deep learning which use this feature based learning to transfer abroad data into higher level and more abstract representation through simple nonlinear elementary structure called neurons has not really been successful in defending itself from manipulation or other attacks from images such as pixel attack and several other manipulations which we have read on Internet.

Gaps your networks come to the rescue with their improve structure such as the capsules which is just a bunch of group of neurons and also with the array how they represent their objects and the topology of the objects whether human or non-human videos audio in full dimension without losing any information which traditional neural networks do.

In this presentation Jerry will give you a walk-through of the overview the motivation of you implementation frameworks and also parts of the breakthrough research that he is doing with his fellow researcher around differentiable manifolds and manifold learning.

Please see bio and headshot for your website.

Tarry is an industry-acknowledged Deep Learning Executive with over 17 years of experience setting up data analytics divisions for F500 multi-nationals. He is currently a mentor at Coursera's DeepLearning Specialization working with Andrew Ng, the world's leading figure in Artificial Intelligence. Expected learners to be trained is around 1.5 million already by end 2018 via a MOOC program. This training was ranked #2 in the world out of 8000 trainings, according to the Inc. Magazine.

He is also an AI and Neuroscience Researcher who works together and seeks guidance from world's leading researchers in deep learning industry.

Tarry works closely with Google's Core TensorFlow team lead in San Francisco to deliver Deep Learning Open Source Platform TensorFlow tutorials for various enterprises across the globe.

Tarry has also recently tied up with a Silicon Valley startup called Re:coded— which was featured on CNNMoney(<http://money.cnn.com/2016/06/01/technology/jobs-syria-coding-flatiron-recoded/index.html>), BBC, TechCrunch, Huffington Post to train deep learning enthusiasts around the world with open source technologies)

He is currently also writing a practical AI / Deep Learning book which is solely aimed to bridge the gap between business and technology by introducing meaningful projects so enterprises can finally move beyond grappling with the currently exploding world of Deep Learning and AI. Book ETA July 2018.

Tarry speaks, keynotes and chairs panels regularly at AI & Deep Learning Tech Conferences held in San Francisco (U.S), Toronto, Montreal (Canada), London (U.K), Finland, Sweden, Germany (Berlin), Guiyang, Beijing Hong Kong (China), Singapore, Turkey, Iraq and more.

In May 2018, he & his co-author will present new research paper on breakthrough Capsules Networks ACM conference in Sweden.(<https://www.icse2018.org>). He is also program committee member of the conference.